

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MODES SHODHAN IN VICHARCHIKA

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurvedic text is sufficient enough to denote that the various skin disorders Kushtha Roga along with their various manifestations were known to Indians from time immemorable. Now a days the Modern Medical Science has many new drugs and investigations have been evaluated even for many incurable skin diseases, but still many conditions in this field are posing a great problem in the field of treatment. The number of cases of skin disorders discarded by the Modern medical field being incurable when submit to Ayurveda for a cure, are reported to get considerable relief and in some cases, they get rid of their ailments completely without any recurrence. This achievement of Ayurvedic modes of treatment in the field of Ayurveda is because of its complete independent and unique fundamental approach towards the treatment of a disease specially in Kushtha Roga. In Ayurveda various skin disorders have been comprehended under the heading of Kushtha which has been classified into. Mahakushtha and Kshudra Kushtha depending upon the extent of the involvement of the Dhatus and vitiation

of Dosha and Doshya in the disease. Though the seat of both the Varieties of Kushtha is mainly skin yet other Dhatus like Rasa, Rakta, Mansa and Lasika along with Tridosha are also involved in the pathogenesis of the Kushtha. All Acharyas are unanimous about the involvement of the Tridosha in the causation of the Kushtha even then Acharya Sushruta has sub classified the Kshudra Kushtha into Vatika Slaishmika and of the Dosha. Vicharchika is a variety of Kshudra Kushtha in which the paitic involvement is prominent. Mainly Lasika is involved in Vicharchika, Principles of treatment for Vicharchika are the same as that of Kushtha.

METHOD OF APPROACH & MATERIAL

Cases were selected from O. P. D. All Necessary examinations were carried out. During the first week patients were, given only placebo treatment in order to assess comparative role of Shodhan in cases of Vicharchika. Classical method of Shodhana was followed.

The various data are represented in the following table:

Karmawise classification is given in (Table No.1) Vaman was given in 7 cases, Virechana was given in 35 cases, Rakta Mokshana was done in 16 cases. Out of 58 cases 35 were male and 23 were female.

The study of chronicity of Disease is between the range of 1 month to 10 years is found.

Age group classification shows that this disease can affect any age group from 1 year to 70 years, though the incidence is more prominent in the age of group of 21 to 50 years.

DISCUSSIONS

The object of this study was to assess the tole of various Modes of Shodhan and to compare the data in order to ascertain effectiveness of an individual mode of Shodhan and superiority or otherwise of these modes of Shodhan, In order to work on this problem Vicharchika was first selected for the study, and various date on the effectiveness of various modes of Shodhan in 58 cases of Vieharchika are represented here, Observation made during the course of Snehan in every Case revealed that even Snehan could inguce considerable relief in important signs and symptoms of Vicharchika such as Kandu, Srav, Pidika and Shyavata. It took about to 5 to 10 days in majority of cases to each the ideal stage of Snehan i. e. Samyak Snehan Avastha. The study of Virechan in cases of these diseases reveals that the improvement starts taking place from next day of Administration of Virechana. Table represents the effectiveness

of mainly Vaman, Virechana and Raktamokshana in cases of Vicharchika, The effect of Vaman was studied in seven Cases and it was found that there was no improvement in main signs and symptoms such as Kandu, Srava, Vaivarnya and Pidika. This table reveals that Virechana was studied in 35 cases of Vicharchika. Srav vanished altogether on 7 day in 20 cases while there was little improvement in Srava in rest of the cases, Kandu disappeared on 4th day in 10 cases and also Pidika disappeared on 4th day in 10 cases. In 25 cases discoloration also improved in 4 days. 16 cases were studied to ascertain the effectiveness of Raktamokshana, Cut of these 16 cases Kandu disappeared on 4th day in these cases. Srav on 7th day in 10 cases, Pidika On 4th day in 10 cases, and Vaivarnya in 5 cases on 4th day. If the results of Virechana and Raktamokshana are compared you can find that in both types of cases Kandu has disappeared in 4 days. Srav in 7 days while Pidika and Vaivarnya also in 4 days. This clearly indicated that results obtained in cases of Virechana & Raktamokshana are completely identical.

A comparative study of Vamana, Virachana and Raktamokshana was done in 58 cases. It shows that Vaman is not effective, Virechana is definitely effective. It was also noted that 100% improvement was obtained by Virechana in some cases. Raktamokshana is also equally effective. It was also noted that effects of Shodhana is quicker in these cases.

The study of improvement in 3 categories. Prashama, Laxnalpata and Alabha, The criteria for defining Prashama was decided to be (75%) for more improvement, Laxnalpata means improvement below (56%) Alabha i, e. no change into the signs and symptoms.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of various facts represented above, it is very clear that Shodhan is a specific treatment in cases of Kshudra Kushtha specially Vicharchika. The results obtained are comparatively quick and last for longer duration. Comparative account of Vaman, Virechana and Raktamokshana indicates that there is no improvement in a group of cases where Vaman was given while there was remarkable improvement in group of Virechana and Raktamokshana. The comparison between Raktamokshana and Virechana shows both of the modes have identical effectiveness.

Table: Karmawise Classification.

Disease	Karma			
	Vaman	Virechana	Raktamokshana	Total
Vicharchika	7	35	16	56

Table: Sex wise classification.

Disease	Sex		
	Male	Female	Total
Vicharchika	35	23	58

Table: Chronicity of Disease.

Disease	Chronicity									
	1M	3 M	6 M	1 Y	2 Y	3 Y	5 Y	10 Y	>10 Y	Total
Vicharchika	6	6	8	6	12	8	4	6	2	58

Table: Result.

Disease	Prashama	Laxanlpta	Alabha	Total
Vicharchika	28	20	10	56

